

Glenna2 Nordic Cloud

Aim 1 Target 4:

Ceph Configuration and Support Best Practice Solutions

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Abstract

Description: Ceph is a free-software storage platform, implements object storage on a single distributed computer cluster which provides interfaces for object-, block- and file-level storage. Ceph is currently deployed by all national Nordic OpenStack providers. The work within Aim1 Target 4 has focused on best practice solution(s) for architectural setup, benchmarking, access patterns, staging and how to mitigate bottlenecks. In addition, solutions for better application scalability and how to setup Rados gateway APIs and how to perform proper maintenance for both object and block store have been investigated.

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What is CEPH?

Ceph is open source software designed to provide highly scalable object-, block- and file-based storage under a unified system.

Ceph storage clusters are designed to run on commodity hardware, using an algorithm called CRUSH (Controlled Replication Under Scalable Hashing) to ensure data is evenly distributed across the cluster and that all cluster nodes can retrieve data quickly without any centralized bottlenecks. Ceph can be used both for static research data that needs to be available for analysis as well as to collect and host cumulating or changing data.

From a technical point of view, Ceph can be used as a modern object storage system which comes with AWS S3¹ and Swift² interfaces. In practice, this means that instead of files, the data is stored as objects in buckets. A bucket is a container for objects that may also include metadata describing the bucket.

The stored objects can be of any data type, such as images or compressed data files. In general, objects are similar to files. Object storage can be used for a variety of purposes. Its concept has benefits but also limitations as lined out below.

Benefits

- Object storage can handle practically any static data.
- Data can be accessed from anywhere using the URL.
- Data can have different levels of access control.
- Data can be replicated between different sites for reliability.

Limitations

- Specific tools are required to use object storage. Object storage cannot be properly mounted for local disk-like usage. There are some tools that can do this, but they have their limitations. For example, *svfs*³ can be used to mount *Swift* as a file system, but it uses *FUSE*⁴ which is slow.
- It is unsuitable for files that change constantly during their lifetime (e.g. most SQL databases).
- The data cannot be modified while it is stored in Ceph. It must be downloaded to a server for processing and the previous version has to be replaced with a new one.

Different ways to use Ceph object storage

You cannot mount Ceph directly to a computer. This means that in order to use the object store, you need software tools to access it.

¹ <https://aws.amazon.com/s3/>

² <https://wiki.openstack.org/wiki/Swift>

³ <https://github.com/ovh/svfs>

⁴ <https://libfuse.github.io/doxygen/index.html>

Within the CSC Ceph environment 'Allas' there are four main ways to access Ceph:

1. In the CSC computing environment, there are ready-to-use tools provided by CSC to access Allas, the CSC Ceph service. These tools are mostly the same that can also be installed in any Linux environment. Allas should be used to store any data that needs to be preserved for longer than a few weeks. The supercomputer's (e.g. Puhti) own storage has a policy to delete idle data, so the data must be moved to Allas after computing.
2. WWW access to Allas is provided by the web interface of the OpenStack cloud environment <https://pouta.csc.fi>. No special software is required to access Allas with a browser, making this the by far simplest way to access Allas. On the other hand, the browser user interface has a number of limitations compared to other clients, the most notable ones are lower performance and uploading/downloading being restricted to only a single file at a time.
3. To access Allas with command line commands, client software supporting the *Swift* or *S3* protocol is required. This is the most flexible way to access Allas, but it requires more effort than other access methods. There are also client libraries available for a variety of languages for programmatic integration of object storage.
4. To access Allas with a GUI client, a suitable GUI client is required. The client needs to be capable to use the *Swift* or *S3* access protocol.

Protocols

The object storage service is provided over two different protocols, *Swift* and *S3*. From the user perspective, one of the main differences between the protocols is authentication. The token-based *Swift* authentication can rely on a variety of protocols to acquire the token, and can be integrated to different identity management solutions. Each token has a limited lifetime. In the key-based *S3*, the user gets an access token/key pair, that can be used to connect to the object storage. The *S3* tokens are practical in many ways, but they include a security aspect: if the server where the tokens are used is compromised, the object storage space will get compromised as well, as the *S3* tokens are not time limited.

Due to this security concern, and due to the wider support for integrating into different identity solutions, *Swift* is the recommended protocol for multiple-user servers, such as Mahti and Puhti. Thus, for example, the CSC-specific *a-commands* as well as the standard *rclone* configuration in the

supercomputer Puhti are based on Swift. However, in some cases, permanent connections as provided by the S3 protocol may be the most reasonable option, for example, in personal virtual machines running within the OpenStack environment

The Swift and S3 protocols are mostly compatible when handling objects. For small objects that do not need to be split during upload, the protocols can be used interchangeably. Large objects need to be split to be uploaded. These objects can be accessed only with both protocols, but e.g. their checksumming is handled differently, and the client may give error messages if they are accessed by the other protocol. The size limit for splitting an object depends on the settings and on the protocol. The limit is typically between 500 MB and 5 GB.

Generic recommendations for selecting the protocol:

- S3 has a wide industry and software support, *Swift* is popular in many scientific collaborations.
- The *Swift* protocol is easier to integrate into identity management.
- In any case, try to use the protocols consistently. Avoid mixing S3 and *Swift* for the same use case.
- It is better to store a few larger objects than many small objects.

Clients

The object storage is accessed via client software that takes care of moving data to and from Ceph and managing data objects. There are several different kinds of client software for accessing the object storage servers. The Ceph object storage implementation can be used with any object storage client that is compatible with the Swift or S3 protocols.

Client	Notes
client	Provides basic functions.
a-commands	Provides easy-to-use tools for basic use. Requires Rclone, Swift and OpenStack. CSC Allas specific.
python-swiftclient	The recommended Swift client.
s3cmd	The recommended S3 client (version 2.0.2 or later).
python-swift-library	
rclone	Useful with supercomputers.
libs3	
python-openstackclient	

aws-cli

aws-cli and the boto3 python library.

curl

Extremely simple to use with public objects and temporary URLs.

wget

Same as curl.

Client operations

1. A *web client* is suitable for using the basic functions. Power users might want to consider the clients *python-swiftclient* and *s3cmd* and in addition *rclone* (not listed in comparison). The table displays the core functions of the power clients concerning data management in a Ceph based environment.

	web-client	swift	s3cmd
Usage	<i>Basic</i>	<i>Power</i>	<i>Power</i>
Create buckets	✓	✓	✓
Upload objects	✓•	✓	✓
List			
objects	✓	✓	✓
buckets	✓	✓	✓
Download			
objects	✓•	✓	✓
buckets		✓	✓
Remove			
objects	✓	✓	✓
buckets	✓••	✓	✓••
Managing access rights			
public/private	✓	✓	✓
read/write access		✓	✓
temp URLs		✓	✓
Move objects		✓	✓
Edit metadata		✓	✓
Upload large files (over 5 GB)		✓	✓
Download whole project		✓	

Remove whole project

- Only one object at a time

- Only empty buckets

Architecture

RADOS (reliable autonomic distributed object store) is the robust, scalable distributed object store used within the Ceph architecture. Ceph's software libraries provide client applications with direct access to the RADOS object-based storage system, and also provide a foundation for some of Ceph's advanced features, including RADOS Block Device (RBD), RADOS Gateway, and the Ceph File System.

The Ceph librados software libraries enable applications written in C, C++, Java, Python and PHP to access Ceph's object storage system using native APIs. The librados libraries provide advanced features, such as partial or complete reads and writes, snapshots, atomic transactions with features like append, truncate and clone range object level key-value mappings.

Ceph also provides a traditional file system interface with POSIX semantics. Object storage systems are a significant innovation, but they complement rather than replace traditional file systems. As storage requirements grow for legacy applications, organizations can configure their legacy applications to also utilize the Ceph file system.

This document specifically concerns the deploying and using of the *radosgw* functionality on top of Ceph.

The CSC deployment architecture

The Ceph components ensure the failure tolerance of your data storage. When you present the data via object storage interfaces, you also need to take into account failure tolerance and load balancing of the customer facing object storage service. I.e. Ceph internals answer the question “How do we make sure that the Ceph radosgw component has access to the stored data”, and here we try to answer the question “How do we make sure customers have access to the Ceph radosgw service”.

Below is a diagram on the CSC Allas object storage deployment, and how these issues have been addressed.

Ceph setup

The design choices for the Ceph installation supporting the Allas service concern mostly the choice of hardware and the storage pool layouts.

The OSD servers, providing the actual storage for the clusters have the following characteristics

- 58 x 2U servers each with
- 2 x 25 gigabit ethernet connectivity
- 2 powerful CPUs. The CPU choice was because of tender technical reasons, and a much lower performance CPU is adequate.
- 192 GB of memory
- 24 x 12 TB SATA disks
- 1 x 3,4 TB NVMe drive

Two classes of storage pools were deployed. One all-NVMe storage pool for object storage metadata pools. The pool stores 3 replicas of the data. Metadata is read and write IOPS heavy, and having low-latency storage for these pools is recommended.

The second pool was a so called erasure encoded pool, with 8 data disks and 3 parity disks. This lowers the performance somewhat, but significantly improves the storage utilization. This pool had NVMe acceleration for internal pool handling, and for write logs.

The NVMe's on the servers were partitioned in smaller parts to support these different use-cases.

The Ceph radosgw servers are virtual machines. On the servers HAProxy handles SSL offloading and ExaBGP handles failure tolerance.

Load balancing

The load balancing for the object storage installation was achieved using DNS. The DNS record of the service points to multiple IPs. The clients randomly choose one of these IPs.

The benefits of using DNS for load balancing instead of e.g. HAProxy is that, in the HAProxy case, all data has to travel through one HAProxy instance. This means that all data has to travel through a single network interface, and you do not get more bandwidth to your service by adding more servers.

Failure tolerance

There are several ways to handle failure tolerance for services like this. We chose BGP (Border Gateway Protocol). Our DNS load balancing forwards the traffic to multiple IPs. In the normal case, if any of those servers fail (crash, has a network break, etc.) a subset of our customers will see downtime.

Here we use BGP and the ExaBGP software component to help. BGP lets your network routers forward traffic to a specific IP to several machines, each having different priorities. The router uses the highest priority IP available for the traffic.

Each server announces two IPs to the router using ExaBGP. Their primary IP with a high priority, and a secondary IP with low priority. E.g. server A reports IP1 as its high priority IP, and IP2 as its low priority IP. Server B reports IP2 as its high priority IP, and IP1 as its low priority IP.

ExaBGP has a health check running to see if the object storage services are working. If the service has failed for some reason, or if ExaBGP stops reporting, the router “forgets” the IPs from that server.

So if server A goes down, it no longer announces IP1 as a high priority IP. The router forward all traffic to server B, which reports IP1 as low priority.

The Ceph Storage Cluster

System Characteristics

When you use the *Ceph radosgw* object storage functionality, the objects are stored in buckets. A bucket is a data object container. Buckets should not be confused with *dockers* or other computing containers. A bucket functions similarly to a file system directory, except that there can only be one level, i.e. buckets cannot contain other buckets. In the following examples are shown from CSC's Ceph based data management solution Allas.

Figure Ceph data structure as in CSC's Ceph environment Allas

Naming buckets

The standard *S3* implementation by AWS has a single namespace for buckets. This means two users can not have buckets with the same name. If one user has a bucket called "test", another bucket called "test" cannot be created. This is configurable in Ceph radosgw, but having a single namespace for buckets allows you for example to access the bucket with its name easily, e.g. <https://bucketname.a3s.fi>. As the single bucket namespace is a standard way of handling the buckets, this practice is adopted in CSC's Allas service.

All bucket names are public, so please do not include any confidential information in the bucket name. You may, for example, use your project ID, e.g. *2000620-raw-data*.

Object URLs can be in the DNS format, e.g. <https://bucketname.a3s.fi/objectname>. Please use a valid DNS name (RFC 1035). We recommend not using upper case or non-ASCII (ä, ö etc.) characters.

It is not possible to rename a bucket.

The Ceph architecture ensures that the data is spread across various servers, which protects against disk and server failures. By default there are no backups of the data, so the Ceph architecture does not protect against accidental or malicious deletion of data.

Benchmarking

To find some bottlenecks of the service we ran "swift upload" in two ways:

1. Create a directory with 3000 3MB files and then
2. "swift upload --object-threads 50 bucket-name /path/to/directory"
3. swift download
4. swift delete
5. repeat
6. Create a 20GB file and "swift upload --use-slo --segment-size 1G --object-threads 1 --segment-threads 1 bucket-name /path/to/file"

3MB because Ceph internally uses 4MB chunks when storing objects.

Monitoring

Object storage specific monitoring uses a Nagios check which uploads, downloads and deletes a 3MB file. It outputs performance data so we can plot it in Grafana. From existing CEPH monitoring we already get metrics of usage in bytes, number of users and buckets. More details about how we monitor & collect metrics from Ceph can be found in the D2-ceph_plus_grafana-Hyvarinen.pdf presentation on <https://wiki.geant.org/display/CISS/1st+SIG-CISS+meeting>

Of course we have our standard monitoring and metrics gathering installed on these object storage machines too. This is a Nagios+Graphite+Grafana+Collectd setup.

- AUTH_url

This is how the URL to an object in a Swift container looks for us now:

```
https://container.pouta.csc.fi/swift/v1/AUTH_project_ID/object
```

One thing that we had to contemplate for a bit was whether we want to expose the OpenStack project UUID in the URL. With Ceph Jewel the most typical model to integrate with OpenStack seems to be using the "AUTH_account" scheme and mapping the "account" to a Project ID in Keystone. In Luminous there seems to be more goodies related to how these mappings can be done, e.g. to individual OpenStack users. But for our purposes mapping to the Project ID was more than enough.

Without the "AUTH_account" scheme we could not find a working configuration for adding quota or exposing relevant information to accounting m2m accounts via admin APIs. It is probably possible to do these things without "AUTH_account" but most of the Swift reference configurations examples do it this way so we went with the flow. It's controlled with this ceph.conf setting:

```
rgw_swift_account_in_url = True
```

Quota

We use Keystone for authentication. After the AUTH_url was enabled, whenever an OpenStack user in a project creates a bucket we get this in the RADOS REST gateway RadosGW:

A new user

A new bucket with the project's UUID set as owner

We decided to set some default quota for all customer projects. This is implemented with a cronjob (if you're interested about the implementation, contact us for more details) which sets a quota with the radosgw-admin command for all projects if they don't already have one. If they do have a set quota, the script leaves it untouched even if the quota doesn't correspond to global values. Thus we can still do manual quota increases for specific projects.

Swift, S3

We thought it would be cool to have both S3 and Swift APIs available. S3 is more popular but Swift is native to OpenStack.

The Swift and S3 protocols that RadosGW implements have different features between RadosGW versions. S3 in RadosGW is different than the S3 service on Amazon and Swift in RadosGW is not the same as the Swift available via the OpenStack Swift project. This means searching for documentation and configuration guides is a bit tricky. Usually docs.ceph.com and Ceph source code has proven most helpful. Unfortunately some information is missing from Jewel documentation specifically, so at times we did have to dig into Ceph source code. Luckily it's laid out in a quite readable manner. Make sure you read the code from the correct branch or tag!

It seems that the Swift API works better. But S3/EC2 credentials are needed with Keystone for getting access to the admin API.

There are some differences between the two protocols in terms of "basic" functionality. Are ACLs compatible for example?

S3 functionality tests with <https://github.com/ceph/s3-tests>

For Swift Testing we couldn't find any so wrote our own in bash. Ideally, we would like to use Rally and Tempest to test Swift.

Ceph.conf:

```
rgw_s3_auth_use_keystone = True
```

Some other related settings in our ceph.conf (excluding ones relating to the admin/service user)

```
rgw_keystone_accepted_roles = object_store_user
```

```
rgw_keystone_api_version = 3
```

```
rgw_keystone_implicit_tenants = False
```

```
rgw_keystone_url = https://cloud.example.com:35357
```

```
rgw_keystone_token_cache_size = 500
```

```
rgw_keystone_revocation_interval = 600
```

Bucket namespace

By having implicit tenants set to 'True' it would make the Ceph bucket name contain the OpenStack project ID. Remember that there is no hierarchy in object storage (except objects go in buckets). This means that normally all buckets are in the same namespace even if they belong to different projects.

The ceph.conf setting that prevents creating buckets with identical names is:

```
rgw_keystone_implicit_tenants = False
```

- Cores / memory configuration

With the rudimentary performance testing we found that a single-threaded client could in our setup eat up all CPU of one of the development object nodes with 1 and 2 cores (and 4GB RAM). For production Phase 1 we started with 8 cores and 16GB RAM on the RadosGW nodes. Assuming near linear scaling this should be able to fill our 10Gb pipes. According to the processes plugin of Collectd the HAProxy process actually showed 3x higher ps_cputime during our stress tests than the radosgw process, possibly because of SSL encryption/decryption. There is probably room for optimization of HAProxy to perform better, but in the meantime cores are cheaper than man-hours.

We realized when doing stress tests in our development environment (where our monolithic OpenStack API nodes only have one core) that, per instance, it would basically DoS Keystone and make Horizon unusable. This was easily fixed by adding an additional core to the API node. This only happened when we tested with a lot of 3MB objects, but was not an issue when uploading large objects with 1 GB segments since the limiting factor was object nodes or the client used. We also managed to improve our Keystone caching and added more keystone threads, so it is no longer a bottleneck.

- To wild card DNS or not?

We started off without a wild card DNS (and certificate). Only S3 uses DNS virtual host style to access buckets, in the end we enabled it and didn't see a lack of functionality - a nice easy win.

- Only https TCP 443 – no HTTP 80 open (no redirect)

Safety first :) But seriously the only problem we found was that the nordugrid-arc-client (which has a presumably rarely used S3 access method) tried only TCP 80. All other clients have been able to cope with only TCP 443 open.

Conclusions

Ceph is a versatile and capable tool for handling general purpose research data storage. The implementation at CSC called Allas has a fast connection to CSC servers and can be used from anywhere on the internet. Allas can be used both for static research data that needs to be available for analysis and to collect and host cumulating or changing data.

In the Allas service the imported data is stored as static objects (object storage). Data can be accessed with S3 or Swift API compatible tools (e.g. WWW, command line, programmatic and graphical interfaces) and the uploaded data can be made accessible over the Internet.

CEPH has so far proved to be quite stable and technically reliable. For the future there will be a focus on taking into use more advanced tools, such as automatic data backups, which are not included in the CSC service at the moment .